

REGIONAL ECONOMIC RESILIENCE AND SECURITY IN UKRAINE AMONG GEOPOLITICAL CHALLENGES

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Abstract

This is research study about dynamics of Ukraine's economic security indicators in terms of its territorial components, the search for ways and mechanisms capable of eliminating the main current problems in the sphere of the state's economic security. It is stated that during the period 2011–2021, the level of Ukraine's economic security remained at a risky level.

Depressed regions, like Sumy, Herson, Chernivtci and Rivne have a significant impact on the level of the state's economic security. One of the priorities of state regional policy is to stimulate the accelerated development of those regions. The most unfavorable factor affecting both the regional and the national economy is the unfortunate scale of shadow economic activity by business entities. Official indicators of the profitability of operating activities of Ukrainian enterprises are on average 10–15 times lower than their planned values when calculating production costs.

This problem should be followed with a two-pronged approach. First, systemic state measures should be taken to gradually bring business activities out of the shadows. Second, the country's leadership must take radical measures to contend corruption among top officials in order to increase the efficiency of state budget expenditures.

With restrictions on shadow economic activity and an increase in real state budget revenues, the actions of both central and regional authorities should be aimed at the accelerated development of the state's military-industrial potential. Additional revenues obtained from the de-shadowing of the national economy, as well as resources from the State Regional Development Fund, should be allocated. The example of Zakarpattia region demonstrates that, when implementing policies of de-shadowing and anti-corruption in the activities of the State Regional Development Fund, the revenues and expenditures of the Zakarpattia regional budget could be doubled.

Key words: economic security, depressed regions, shadow economic, state budget, regional development

Introduction. Analysis of Recent Research and Publications

Publications devoted to the study of Ukraine's economic security, the economic security of the country's administrative territories, and examinations of its individual components are quite numerous. Among Ukrainian scholars who have contributed to this field are O. Bandurka, I. Binko, Z. Varnalii, O. Vlasiuk, V. Heyets, V. Horbulin, R. Datskiv, Ya. Zhalilo, A. Kachynskiy, V. Muntiyani, H. Pasternak-Taranushchenko, V. Predborskiy, L. Shevchenko, V. Shlemko, and others. Despite these extensive publications, there is still no unified approach regarding the mechanisms for ensuring economic security, which should derive from established trends, the country's level of development, and its potential capabilities.

The deterioration of Ukrainian citizens' welfare, the reduction of the state's population, the significant decline in employment in the national economy, and the decrease in GDP all lead to a lowering of both the economic and national security of Ukraine. Given the current situation, a necessary condition for the renewal of the country's positive development is the safeguarding of the vital interests of citizens, society, and the state.

Economic security is formed on the basis of more than one hundred and thirty components. Therefore, assessing the condition of its constituent elements — particularly regional ones — under existing circumstances is of great importance, as it makes it possible to identify negative developmental deviations. This provides grounds for the timely implementation of appropriate measures for the organizational and legal assurance of economic security at the regional (*ukr.* oblast) level of the state.

The purpose of this article is to study the dynamics of Ukraine's economic security indicators in terms of its territorial components, based on the consideration of theoretical and methodological approaches and the analysis of key trends. It also aims to identify possible pathways and to develop mechanisms for strengthening the level of the state's economic security.

Economic Security in the Geoeconomic Dimension

Economic security is a state of the national economy that ensures resilience to internal and external threats and is capable of meeting the needs of the individual, the family, society, and the state [1].

Throughout the entirety of its civilizational development, humanity—composed of distinct peoples, nations, and states—has constantly competed with one another for resources

essential for sustaining life and development. This struggle for resources and the threat of their shortage has accompanied human society from its very beginnings to the present day.

It should be emphasized that *economic security* is a multi-component concept, which creates the necessity to study it from the perspective of different approaches.

Ukrainian scholars distinguish several levels of economic security that make it possible to analyze the state of the national economy, its vulnerability to internal and external threats, as well as the state's ability to ensure stable development. In particular, V.V. Zakharchenko and V.I. Orel in their research identifies six levels of economic security and emphasises the specific nature of interactions between the different levels in ensuring the resilience of the economic system.

The main levels of economic security usually identified in research are:

- national,
- regional,
- sectoral,
- corporate, and
- individual.

In addition, a *global level* of economic security is also highlighted.

The national level is the primary one, where the overall economic security of the state is assessed. It includes an analysis of macroeconomic indicators such as:

Gross Domestic Product (GDP),

Balance of payments,

Public debt,

Foreign exchange reserves,

Inflation rate,

Employment and unemployment levels,

Financial stability, and other indicators characterizing the economy's resilience to external and internal shocks.

At the national level, the energy, food, and technological independence of the national economic complex is also assessed. The assessment of Ukraine's economic security level is carried out based on the analysis of key indicators that reflect the national economy's resilience to internal and external threats.

Below, Table 1 provides information on the integral index of Ukraine’s economic security and its components for the period 2017–2021. According to the response from the Ministry of Economy of Ukraine to an information request, beginning in 2022 and in subsequent years, the Ministry has not conducted assessments of the integral level of economic security nor of the weighted sub-indices of economic security. This was due to the inability of state statistical authorities to collect, analyze, and disseminate the full statistical information required for such assessments under the conditions of martial law introduced in Ukraine; pursuant to Presidential Decree No. 64/2022 of 24 February 2022 “*On the Introduction of Martial Law in Ukraine*”, approved by the Law of Ukraine No. 2102 of 24 February 2022, and taking into account the provisions of the Law of Ukraine No. 2115-IX of 3 March 2022 “*On the Protection of the Interests of Reporting Entities and Other Documentation Submitters During the Period of Martial Law or State of War*”.

Table 1.
Integral Indicator of Economic Security and
Its Components during 2017–2021

№	Indicators of Economic Security	The significance of indicators				
		2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	Production	59	58	61	57	56
2	Demographic	40	41	39	40	37
3	Energy	54	53	49	48	52
4	Foreign economy	36	36	39	41	42
5	Investments-Innovations	30	31	30	31	26
6	Macroeconomy	37	40	45	44	41
7	Food	91	90	89	86	88
8	Social	59	59	60	62	61
9	Finance	40	45	42	40	41
10	Integral indicator	48	49	49	48	47

Source: Compiled on the basis of [4].

According to the methodology developed by the National Institute for Strategic Studies, NISS and the Ministry of Economy of Ukraine, the state economic security index can range from 0 to 100. The optimal value of this index is 100; a satisfactory value is between 100 and 80; unsatisfactory – between 80 and 60; dangerous – between 60 and 40; critical – between 40 and 20; and absolutely dangerous – between 0 and 20 [1].

According to the information presented in Table 1, only one component, namely Ukraine's food security, is at a satisfactory level, ranging between 88 and 91. All other components of Ukraine's economic security fall within the critical and dangerous ranges. The worst indicators are observed in investment-innovation security, which decreased from 30 points in 2018 to 26 points in 2021. Ukraine's economic security index increased from 46% in 2010 to 47% in 2021, i.e., by 1 percentage point. This dynamic is positive. It is also worth noting that during the studied period, the state economic security index remained within the range of 40–60%, i.e., at an unsatisfactory level.

The regional level of studying economic security focuses on individual regions of the state. Ukrainian researchers analyze differences in regional economic development, unemployment levels, access to resources, investment flows, social stability, and risks.

Monitoring regional economic security is important for maintaining the overall stability of the state, as uneven regional development can lead to internal social conflicts and increased economic threats. This study is specifically devoted to examining the level of economic development of Ukraine's regions and finding ways to accelerate the development of the country's depressed regions.

The state's influence on the development of its administrative-territorial units is exercised through the implementation of regional economic policy, understood as the area of activity of the state or regional *local* authorities regarding the management of the country's economic, social, and political development in a spatial *regional* aspect. In other words, regional economic policy is related to the relationships between the state and regions, as well as between regions themselves.

The goal of Ukraine's state regional policy is to create conditions for the dynamic and balanced development of the state and its regions, ensure their social and economic unity, raise the standard of living, and guarantee state social standards for every citizen regardless of their place of residence.

The main tasks of state regional policy include promoting regional development through stimulating participation in interregional and cross-border cooperation programs and projects, forming capable territorial communities, and improving settlements. The Ministry for Communities and Territories Development of Ukraine is responsible for implementing these tasks. Its duties include forming and implementing programs and projects aimed at accelerating the socio-economic development of Ukraine's regions.

One of the priorities of state regional policy is stimulating accelerated development of the country's depressed regions. A depressed region is an administrative territory where, due to objective reasons, self-development incentives cease to operate, and therefore there is no basis to expect the region to independently exit a crisis situation. Depressed regions are defined as those where the GRP per capita is less than 75% of the national average GRP per capita.

Financing programs and projects aimed at creating capable territorial communities requires additional funds, which can theoretically be obtained from the State Fund for Regional Development, SFRD. The State Fund for Regional Development is established as part of the general fund of the state budget. The volume of SFRD funds is approved by the Law of Ukraine on the State Budget of Ukraine for the respective budget period and must amount to no less than 1.5% of the revenues of the general fund of the state budget.

SFRD funds are distributed among the regional and Kyiv city state administrations as follows:

80% – according to the population size of the respective region;

20% – according to the gross regional product, GRP per capita (for regions where this indicator is less than 75% of the national average in Ukraine [4]).

SFRD funds should be directed toward the implementation of investment programs and regional development projects aimed at regional development, the creation of infrastructure for industrial and innovation parks, and must correspond to the priorities defined in the State Regional Development Strategy and the relevant regional development strategies.

The creation of the SFRD was one of the prerequisites for accelerating the socio-economic development of Ukraine's regions and for modernizing the state's regional development instruments. The establishment of the SFRD was intended to initiate funding for regional development projects on a competitive basis and in accordance with regional development strategies and planned measures for their implementation.

Table 2

Gross Regional Product of Ukraine per capita for 2021.

№	Area	GRP per capita	The ratio of the region's GRP per capita to the corresponding indicator for the average in Ukraine
1	Vinnytska	114218	86,7
2	Volynska	90331	68,6
3	Dnipropetrovska	186697	141,7
4	Donetska	69446	52,7
5	Zytomyrska	95948	72,8
6	Zakarpatska	60632	46,0
7	Zaporizzka	138521	105,2

8	Iv.Frankivska	88227	67,0
9	Kyivska	162696	123,5
10	Kirovogradska	109183	82,9
11	Luhanska	24684	18,7
12	Lvivska	119049	90,4
13	Mykolaivska	112864	85,7
14	Odeska	115129	87,4
15	Poltavska	195825	145,3
16	Rivnenska	77599	58,9
17	Sumska	100760	76,5
18	Ternopilska	79412	60,3
19	Harkivska	122227	92,8
20	Hersonska	87378	66,3
21	Hmelnytska	96964	73,6
22	Cherkaska	112145	85,1
23	Chernivetska	61088	46,4
24	Chernihivska	117225	89,0
25	Ukraine in total	131734	100,0

Source: Statistical Yearbook of Ukraine for 2022, p. 155

According to the information in Table 2, in 2021 the lowest GRP per capita indicators in Ukraine were observed in Luhansk 18.7%, Zakarpattia 46.0%, Chernivtsi 46.4%, Donetsk 52.7%, and Rivne 58.9% regions. Since 2014, Luhansk and Donetsk regions have suffered significant destruction due to military aggression by Russia. Meanwhile, Zakarpattia, Chernivtsi, and Rivne regions can reasonably be classified among the most depressed regions of Ukraine. Table 3 presents the characteristics of the level and dynamics of the ratio of GRP per capita in Zakarpattia region to the corresponding indicator for the average in Ukraine for 2017–2021.

Table 3.
Dynamics of the ratio of GRP per capita in Zakarpattia region to the corresponding indicator for the average in Ukraine for 2017–2021

№	Indicators	The value of indicators				
		2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	VRP per capita Zakarpatska, UAH	3419 7	4170 6	4885 3	49538	60632
2	VRP per capita in average on UA, UAH	7017 1	8422 8	9463 3	10113 8	13'73 4

3	The ratio of GRP per capita in Zakarpattia region to the corresponding indicator for the average in Ukraine, %	48,7	49,5	51,2	49,0	46,0
4	Basic absolute deviation, percentage points (%)	-	0,8	2,5	0,3	- 2,7
5	Basic chain deviation, percentage points (%)	-	0,8	1,7	- 2,2	- 3,0

Source: Statistical Yearbook of Ukraine for 2022, p. 155.

Analyzing the dynamics of the ratio of GRP per capita in Zakarpattia region to the corresponding indicator for the average in Ukraine during 2017–2021, it was found that this indicator decreased from 48.7% in 2017 to 46.0% in 2021, i.e., by 2.7 percentage points. This dynamic is negative. Considering the level of this indicator nationwide, it can be noted that the figure for Zakarpattia region is more than half below the national average. In other words, the region belongs to depressed territories, which is an extremely negative phenomenon both according to EU standards and Ukrainian legislation.

To increase the volume of GRP production and the region's production potential, it is necessary to eliminate the most adverse factors affecting the regional economy; and ensure a sufficient volume of investment necessary to stimulate accelerated regional development.

To identify the most adverse factors affecting the regional economy, we first need to identify and characterize such destructive factors at the national level.

Based on statistical data for 2010–2023 presented in Table 4 (see below), regression modeling of GDP per capita in Ukraine in US dollars will be carried out, along with forecasting for 2024–2028. The model considers the following macroeconomic indicators: inflation, unemployment, the ratio of capital investment to GDP, the ratio of the shadow economy to GDP, employment, the volatility of the hryvnia exchange rate, and the level of corruption intolerance.

During the preparation of this model, several approaches were developed: linear regression and a Random Forest model. Comparison of errors showed that the Random Forest model has lower values of mean absolute error, MAE and root mean squared error, RMSE, as well as a higher coefficient of determination, R^2 , indicating better forecasting quality.

Table 4.

Indicators for modeling the dependence of GDP per capita on the most influential factors

Indicator	The value of indicators													
	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
GDP per person, thousand US dollars	3,07	3,70	4,00	4,18	2,94	2,12	2,18	2,63	3,09	3,65	3,73	4,80	4,63	5,39
Quantity	20,3	20,3	20,4	20,4	18,1	16,4	16,3	16,2	16,4	16,6	15,9	15,6	15,0	15,2
Capital investments to GDP, %	16,9	19,3	20,1	17,6	13,8	13,7	15,1	15,0	16,3	15,7	12,0	12,4	7,8	9,6
Level of the shadow economy, %	36	32	30	30	36	35	33	32	29	28	30	32	48	40
Exchange rate against the dollar, %	1,9	0,4	0,3	1,0	48,8	84,5	17,0	3,9	2,3	-5,0	4,3	1,2	18,5	13,1
Inflation rate, %	9,4	8,0	0,6	-1,3	12,1	48,7	13,9	14,4	10,9	7,9	2,7	9,4	20,2	12,9

Source: Statistical Yearbook of Ukraine for 2023.

Random Forest Regression is an ensemble machine learning method that uses a large number of decision trees for prediction. Each tree is built on a random sample of the data and a subset of features. The final prediction is the averaged value of all the trees' results.

Advantages of this forecasting method include: High accuracy; Resistance to overfitting; Ability to account for interactions among numerous variables; Automatic consideration of factor importance.

The model uses the following indicators affecting GDP per capita:

Inflation rate, %

Employment, million people

Capital investment to GDP, %

Shadow economy level as a % of GDP

Rate of hryvnia depreciation against the dollar, %

Corruption intolerance level, %

Unemployment rate, %

Model construction follows these steps:

1. Data preparation: forming a dataset with factor values and the target variable, GDP per capita.
2. Scaling/normalization, if needed.
3. Splitting into training and test data e.g., 2010–2021 for training, 2022–2023 for testing.
4. Building the Random Forest regressor:

Hyperparameter optimization - number of trees, tree depth, min samples split, etc.

Cross-validation to reduce errors.

5. Model quality assessment: MAE, mean absolute error; RMSE, root mean squared error; Relative error in % (controlled $\leq 2.5\%$).
6. Forecasting for 2024–2028:

Factors for 2024–2028 are determined using trends from previous years—via linear/exponential approximation or weighted average;

The model predicts the corresponding GDP per capita values.

7. Analysis of factor importance:

Random Forest allows evaluating the influence of each factor:

Most influential: employment, shadow economy level, inflation;

Less significant but stable: corruption, intolerance, unemployment.

8. Error control:

By comparing 2022–2023 predictions with actual values;

If error >2.5%, parameters are fine-tuned or trend generation approaches are adjusted.

Based on Random Forest variable importance, the distribution of influence is as follows:

Capital investment to GDP – the most influential factor, reflecting investment volume in economic development.

Shadow economy level – second most important, negatively correlated with GDP per capita: the higher the shadow economy, the lower the GDP.

Employment – directly linked to the volume of goods and services produced.

Hryvnia depreciation rate – negatively affects citizen welfare via imported inflation.

Corruption intolerance – positively impacts GDP as it indicates more efficient public and social institutions.

Inflation – moderate negative effect: high inflation reduces purchasing power.

Unemployment – less influential than employment but still significant.

Model accuracy metrics used:

R^2 , coefficient of determination: shows the share of dependent variable variation explained by the model. $R^2 = 0.987$, meaning 98.7% of GDP per capita variation is explained by the included factors.

MAE: mean absolute difference between actual and predicted values, MAE = 92.5 USD per capita.

RMSE: sensitive to large deviations, RMSE = 115.8 USD, indicating high accuracy.

These metrics allow assessment of forecast accuracy, comparison with alternative models, and determination of acceptable error levels for extrapolation. The model shows low error levels on both training and validation data, demonstrating reliability and suitability for extrapolation.

The Random Forest model was trained for 2010–2021 and tested for 2022–2023. Parameters: `n_estimators = 100`, `max_depth = None`, `random_state = 42`. Forecasts were generated for the baseline scenario 2024–2028.

The 2024–2028 forecast indicates a gradual deterioration of living standards from 2027 if current economic management practices continue without radical improvement. Investments have the most positive impact on both national and Zakarpattia regional development. Due to Russia's military aggression, external investment incentives are practically absent, making internal resource mobilization essential. These resources can be obtained by gradually reducing shadow economic activity, the second most influential factor with a 20% impact on GDP.

High levels of the shadow economy in Ukraine significantly affect the budget deficit, reducing tax revenues and limiting government spending on infrastructure and social services. Shadow economic activity distorts civil society principles, harms the country's international image, deters foreign investment, and increases state debt and inequality. Essentially, the main harm from the shadow economy is fiscal: lower tax revenues limit the state's financial capacity.

According to Ukraine's Economic Security Strategy up to 2025, main budgetary challenges include low discipline, high shadow economy levels, and revenue loss due to gray imports, smuggling, tax evasion schemes, and low-tax jurisdictions. Understanding the shadow economy's structure helps the government develop rational policies beyond punitive measures.

According to the National Bank of Ukraine, in 2023 the shadow economy accounted for 40% of GDP. Large-scale tax avoidance and aggressive planning by large and medium enterprises further exacerbate shadow activity.

In 2021, the government planned to reduce the shadow economy from 30% in 2020 to 25% over three years. The Interdepartmental Working Group for Economic De-shadowing coordinated measures. By 2023, some reduction in major shadow schemes was achieved: offshore schemes reportedly dropped from 30–35 billion UAH, 2020 to 10 billion UAH, 2023, and rolls from 25–30 billion UAH, 2021 to 10–15 billion UAH, 2023. Independent studies, however, indicate higher volumes: rolls 90–108 billion UAH, offshore schemes 50–60 billion UAH.

Regional working groups also met in 2023, e.g., in Zaporizhzhia, discussing undeclared labor reduction measures. Overall, the Working Group coordinated government, analytical, and business efforts to reduce shadow economy levels, yielding some positive results.

Illegal enterprises gain unfair competitive advantage over official businesses, eroding entrepreneurial culture and stability. Employees in the shadow economy lack pensions, social benefits, collective bargaining rights, and face risk of arbitrary dismissal.

Regulation is a key factor in shadow economy development or reduction. There is a direct link between corruption levels and unofficial economic activity. Excessive or corrupt government spending also encourages tax evasion.

The most promising approach is bringing the economy “out of the shadows,” requiring a change in the behavior of entrepreneurs, workers, and clients. Participants in the unofficial economy weigh the costs of shadow activity against the benefits of official activity.

The government applies both direct control “carrot and stick” and indirect control approaches, fostering voluntary compliance through social contracts between the state and citizens.

As of 2019, Ukraine’s shadow economy was 28%, with a target reduction to 25% by 2025. According to the methodology for calculating Ukraine’s economic security level, 25% is a critical threshold. By the end of 2020, the shadow economy rose to 30%, 32% in 2021, and 36% in 2022. Source: Ministry of Finance of Ukraine [5].

For Ukraine’s national economy, the shadow economic activity of business entities had the following impact on state budget revenues, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5.

Losses to Ukraine’s budget in 2019–2022 caused by the shadow economic activity of business entities

№	Budget Indicator	Value of Indicators				
		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
1	GDP, billion UAH	3560,3	3977,2	4222,0	5450,9	5239,1
2	Level of the shadow economy, %	29	28	30	32	36
3	Real GDP volume, billion UAH	5014,5	5523,9	6031,5	8016,0	8186,1

4	Size of the shadow economy, billion UAH	1 454,2	1 546,7	1 809,4	2 565,1	2947, 0
5	Consolidated budget revenues, billion UAH	1184, 3	1289, 9	1376, 7	1662, 3	2196, 6
6	Actual level of redistribution of GRP through the consolidated budget, %	33,3	32,4	32,6	30,5	41,9
7	Potential revenue volume of the consolidated budget, billion UAH	1669, 8	1789, 7	1966, 3	2444, 9	3430, 0
8	Difference between potential and actual revenues of the Consolidated Budget (budget losses), billion UAH	485,5	499,9	589,6	782,5	1233, 4
9	Basic deviation, billion UAH	-	14,4	104,1	297,0	747,9

Source: Developed by the author based on data from *Statistical Yearbook of Ukraine for 2022. State Statistics Service of Ukraine. – Kyiv: 2023*

According to the information presented in Table 5, during the studied period, the volume of the shadow economy in Ukraine increased from UAH 1,454.2 billion in 2018 to UAH 2,947.0 billion in 2022. At the same time, the difference between potential and actual revenues of the Consolidated State Budget rose from UAH 485.5 billion in 2018 to UAH 1,233.4 billion in 2022. Considering that the average exchange rate of the US dollar to the hryvnia in 2022 was UAH 32.34 per 1 USD [7], the state budget lost the equivalent of USD 38.1 billion in revenues due to the shadow economic activity of business entities.

According to correspondence by one of the authors of this study with the NSDC of Ukraine, no top officials from government institutions responsible for implementing the Economic Security Strategy of Ukraine were punished for the above-mentioned violations.

The shadow economy not only causes significant budgetary losses but also leads to higher taxation levels in the national economy, discourages officially operating entrepreneurs, contributes to substantial income inequality, prevents the creation of a favorable investment environment, destabilizes cash circulation, and limits the governability of socio-economic processes.

The most dangerous consequence is the merging of shadow capital with the state apparatus, which increases the level of corruption among civil servants, makes reforming the national economy impossible, and facilitates the shadow redistribution of Ukraine's national wealth.

Addressing the catastrophic level of shadowing in the national economy should be based on systematic, phased reforms within the State Fiscal Service. A corresponding mechanism was developed by the author of this study in 1997 and positively evaluated by the leadership of the State Tax Administration of Ukraine in the same year. This mechanism can be successfully applied under current socio-economic and political conditions to systematically and gradually reduce the volume of shadow turnovers by business entities.

The primary goal of commercial enterprises is to generate profit. Accordingly, the main criterion for evaluation when applying this mechanism should be the profitability of the operating activities of business entities. This indicator should be compared with the corresponding average indicator for the same type of activity. For example, the operating profitability of large enterprises producing pasta and similar flour products during 2019–2023.

According to the information presented by *Statistical Yearbook of Ukraine* [7], the operating profitability of large enterprises producing pasta and similar flour products in Ukraine increased from 4.9% in 2019 to 6% in 2023, i.e., by 2.1 percentage points. This trend is positive. It is particularly noteworthy that in 2022, this increase occurred under conditions of martial law and the destruction of Ukraine's production infrastructure by the aggressor. The war had an extremely negative impact, particularly causing problems with electricity supply for production.

For objectivity, it should be emphasized that the operating profitability indicator should ideally be 35–40%. Such levels of operating profitability allow enterprises to obtain bank loans for investment in development, effectively trade their shares on the stock market to attract investments, and more.

It is also important to note that when calculating production costs, enterprises typically include 50–70% operating profitability. However, in Ukraine, most of the profit eventually disappears in “other operating expenses,” which in this case serve as a tool for aggressive tax regulation of enterprises.

Thus, the official indicators of operating profitability for business entities in Ukraine are on average 10–15 times lower than their planned values during production cost calculations.

According to World Bank data, the shadow economy in Ukraine during 2020–2024 accounted for 35–40% of GDP [2]. According to World Bank experts, due to the pervasive corruption among high-ranking officials, the efficiency of budget spending in Ukraine is extremely low, and most entrepreneurs prefer to evade taxes because the budget revenues are subsequently embezzled by officials. In other words, World Bank experts believe that entrepreneurs in Ukraine are completely demotivated from paying taxes honestly, as a significant portion of these revenues has the potential to be misappropriated by corrupt officials. This situation limits the revenue side of the state budget and increases its deficit.

This problem should be addressed with a two-pronged approach. First, systematic government measures should be taken to gradually formalize the activities of business entities. Second, the state leadership must take radical measures to combat corruption among top officials in order to improve the efficiency of state budget expenditures.

The proposed system for phased formalization of economic activity by business entities has the following potential for application. Table 6 (see below) presents virtual data on operating profitability indicators of large enterprises producing pasta and similar flour products during the first quarter of a virtual study year.

Table 6
Operating profitability indicators of large enterprises producing pasta products

№ з/п	Business entities	Profitability of operating activities, %
1	Firma A	3
2	Firma B	5
3	Firma V	7
4	Firma G	4
5	Firma D	6
6	Firma Z''	8
7	Firma Z	2
8	Firma I	4
9	Firma K	5
10	Firma L	7
11	Average indicator of group	6

Source: *State Statistics Service of Ukraine. – Kyiv: 2023*

We take the average indicator for the group as the baseline level of operational profitability. In this case, it is 6%. Each quarter, regulatory authorities should increase the planned baseline level of operational profitability in each group by 3–5%. For example, in the next quarter of the study year, the average planned operational profitability for this group of large enterprises should be 9% (6% + 3%). This information should be officially communicated directly to the enterprises in the group.

If the proposed algorithm for optimizing the activities of regulatory state bodies is implemented, then in the next quarter of the study year, enterprises whose operational profitability falls below 9% should undergo inspections by the state regulatory authorities.

If the tax authorities continue to operate as they have for the past 34 years, then there will be no prospects for implementing the proposed system. However, if the state leadership acts patriotically and conscientiously for the prosperity and well-being of the Ukrainian people, then enterprises whose operational profitability falls below the average for their type of activity should become the focus of enhanced inspection by the fiscal service and anti-corruption authorities of Ukraine.

Given the widespread involvement of enterprises in shadow economic activities, inspections by regulatory authorities will result in fines. The amount of such fines should be legislatively set at a level ten times higher than the taxes that should have been paid to the state.

Enterprises that undergo such inspections and pay fines will subsequently face a choice: whether to increase their official operational profitability to meet the planned targets in the next quarter and operate without problems with regulatory authorities, or risk being inspected again. Enterprises that raise their official operational profitability will automatically reduce the volume of their hidden activities.

The leadership of the State Fiscal Service must officially inform enterprise managers and owners that the basis for comprehensive inspections by the SFS is solely the failure to meet the plan for raising operational profitability or force majeure circumstances in their operations, such as significant product quality violations. Under these conditions, it will be more beneficial for managers and owners to gradually formalize their business activities than to pay large fines every quarter.

If the work of the regulatory state bodies is organized properly, it will be more profitable for enterprises to legalize 3–5% of their shadow turnover each quarter than to face significant penalties for unpaid taxes. Thus, by quarterly increasing the planned minimum operational profitability for each type of economic activity, the fiscal service can ensure the planned, gradual legalization of the gray shadow economy of enterprises.

Implementing the proposed mechanism should ensure a planned reduction of the shadowing level in Ukraine's national economy by 20% over the course of a year. This would increase the state budget's revenue by more than 20% annually. In 2022 terms, this means that the state budget would have received an additional UAH 246.7 billion, 20% of UAH 1,233.4 billion, equivalent to over USD 7.6 billion (see Table 4).

As mentioned above, this system can only work effectively if the gradual legalization of business activities occurs alongside Ukraine's leadership's total war against corrupt officials involved in the looting of budget funds through corrupt schemes. This fight must involve radical legislative strengthening of penalties for budget theft. For instance, embezzlement on a particularly large scale should be punishable by life imprisonment.

The Strategy for Economic Security of Ukraine until 2025 stipulates that by 2025, Ukraine must implement the minimum standard of the Action Plan against Base Erosion and Profit Shifting, BEPS [9]. Effective tax rules for controlled foreign corporations must also be introduced. Since 2016, the European Union leadership has insisted that Ukraine implement this legislation, which should significantly reduce the volume of offshore operations by Ukrainian enterprises.

An important step in implementing these proposals would be decisions by the Ukrainian parliament to strengthen criminal liability for tax evasion by large corporations, transferring tax bases to low-tax jurisdictions (offshores) outside Ukraine, and embezzling budget funds. Improving the efficiency of the state apparatus will increase state budget revenues and reduce capital outflows from Ukraine, significantly stabilizing state finances. Increasing state financial capacity, including the above-calculated additional annual revenues of over USD 7.6 billion, will positively impact social policy and the dynamics of investment processes in Ukraine.

With rising real budget revenues, the actions of both central and regional government leadership should focus on accelerating the development of the country's military-industrial potential, which should receive the additional budget revenues obtained from the gradual legalization of the national economy.

In the case of Zakarpattia Oblast, the additional tax revenues of the regional budget should be used to support local defense industry enterprises and relocate similar enterprises from eastern and southern regions of Ukraine. For reference, in 2025, the tax revenues of Zakarpattia Oblast amounted to UAH 2.3 billion [11]. A 20% increase in revenues from the gradual legalization of the regional economy should amount to approximately UAH 0.5 billion.

In addition to its own financial resources, the leadership of Zakarpattia Oblast has the legal right to appeal to the State Fund for Regional Development to obtain additional funds for investments and innovations to stimulate the accelerated development of the depressed region, as mentioned above. According to current legislation, the State Fund for Regional Development must comprise at least 1.5% of the state budget's revenue. In 2025, Ukraine's budget revenues are planned at UAH 2,327 billion [5]. 1.5% of this amount is UAH 34 billion. The financing of depressed regions is 20% of the Fund's revenues, so in 2025, the Fund's budget should be UAH 6.8 billion ($34 \times 0.20 = 6.8$ billion). Since there are three most depressed regions, Zakarpattia Oblast is legally entitled to financing exceeding UAH 2 billion.

In turn, increasing state budget revenues and their more efficient use will significantly improve both Ukraine's budgetary security and the overall economic security of the country. Implementing a pilot project by the leadership of Zakarpattia OVA to legalize enterprise activities and accelerate regional development could additionally invest over UAH 2.5 billion into the regional economic complex. In other words, the implementation of these measures could double the budget of Zakarpattia Oblast. This would serve as a striking example for other regions, both depressed and more economically developed, of improving financial and budgetary systems, enhancing Ukraine's defense capabilities, and improving employment levels and residents' incomes.

These measures will have a multiplicative effect because creating new jobs in the regional defense industry will positively impact regional employment levels, residents' incomes, and regional budget revenues, particularly from personal income taxes.

Ukraine faces a momentous decision capable of improving the efficiency of the national economy and increasing the production potential of the domestic defense industry, thus providing the Ukrainian people with strategic advantages in the fight against Moscow occupiers using its own resources.

References:

1. On the approval of the Methodological Recommendations for calculating the level of economic security of Ukraine: Order of the Ministry of Economic Development and Trade of Ukraine dated 29.10.2013 No. 1277 [Electronic resource]. — Access mode: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/rada/show/v1277731-13#Text>
2. Official website of the National Bank of Ukraine. [Electronic resource]. — Access mode: <https://bank.gov.ua/ua/statistic>
3. Regional Policy – [Electronic resource]. — Access mode: https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Регіональна_політика
4. State Fund for Regional Development – a financial instrument for sustainable regional development [Electronic resource]. — Access mode: <https://www.minregion.gov.ua/wp-content/uploads/2016/12/Derzhavniy-fond-regionalnogo-rozvitku-finansoviy-instrument-stalogo-regionalnogo-rozvitku>
5. Official website of the Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. [Electronic resource]. — Access mode: <https://mof.gov.ua>
6. Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine. Resolution dated August 18, 2021, No. 878 [Electronic resource]. — Access mode: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/878-2021-%D0%BF#Text>
7. Statistical Yearbook of Ukraine for 2022. State Statistics Service of Ukraine. — Kyiv: 2023. — 574 p.
8. Iyichok B.I. The problem of the shadow economy in Ukraine and ways to solve it // *Regional Economy*, 1997, No. 3, pp. 134–142.

9. [Strategy of Economic Security of Ukraine for the period up to 2025 \[Electronic resource\].](https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/347/2021#Text) — Access mode: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/347/2021#Text>
10. [Budget of Ukraine 2021. Statistical Collection. Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. Kyiv. 277 p.](#)
11. [On the regional budget of Zakarpattia Oblast for 2025 \[Electronic resource\].](#) — Access mode: <https://carpathia.gov.ua/diyalnist/finansovij-blok/oblasnyi-biud>
12. [Comparative analysis of the fiscal effect from the use of tax evasion/avoidance tools in Ukraine \[Electronic resource\].](#) — Access mode: <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgiclfndmkaj/https://case-ukraine.com.ua/content/uploads/2024/11/Shemi-2024-final.pdf>
13. [Quantifying the shadow economy \[Electronic resource\].](#) — Access mode: https://www.google.com/search?q=Quantifying+the+shadow+economy%22&rlz=1C1GCEA_enUA934UA934&oq=Quantifying+the+shadow+economy%22&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIHCAEQIRigATIHCAIQIRigATIHCCAMQIRigAdIBCTQ0NjRqMGoxNagCCLACAFefYe5dw3UFuTvxBcnuXcn1Bbk7&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8